

Usman Nasir Nature Guest

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Annotation:

This article discusses the depiction of nature in the works of Usmon Nosir. His poems reflect the relationship between humans and nature.

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Namangan is a place where many of the best writers and scientists of its time grew up. In particular, Boborahim Mashrab, a major representative of Uzbek classical literature, grew up in this country. Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur spent his youth here . Also, Fazli, Nadir, Ghazi , Majzub, Munshi, Mukhlis, Makhzun, Nadim, Shavqi, Ibrat, Umrzaq Khayrati, Khilvati, Sofizoda, Rafiq Mo'min, Osman Nasir and others made a significant contribution to the treasury of Uzbek literature. Many poets created on this land. Namangan Zafar Diyar, Yoldosh Shamsharov, Parda Tursun, Chustiy, Shohi, Jonrid Abdullakhanov, Turgun Polat, Nuriddin Bobohojaev, Husniddin Sharipov, Hamidjon Hamidiy, Azimjon Rahimov, Odiljon Nasirov, Habib Sadulla, Dadakhan Nuri, Ermuhammad Nurmatov, Abdugani Abduvaliev, Ahmad Tursun, Nurbek Abdullaev, Yaqubjon Ahmadjonov, Sadiq Sayhun, Ziyaviddin Mansurov contributed to the Uzbek literature.

Osman Nasser! When this name is mentioned, in Uzbek literature, the image of a poet who is always in awe and hasty, who is threshing in his work and who dreams in his life comes to mind. It is unbelievable that the owner of a pen with a salty forehead became a prisoner of a cruel society. After all, in his poems, we do not find criticisms of the society, there is not the slightest attempt to smear the times .

difficult past and past made him grow up early. He stood out among his peers due to his ambition, sharp intelligence, and high talent. It is a fact that he was lucky enough to travel to Russia in the company of his excellent peers when he was still a schoolboy , and even recited a new poem he had written for the workers at the factory called Putilov by heart and amazed Russian speakers.

entered the pedagogy in Samarkand (now SamDU) in 1932. A young student who has mastered the Russian language like his mother tongue, goes to Northern cities during his annual vacation, and then to the Caucasus. "The charming scenery of the Black Sea coast fascinates him. Bathe in healing springs in Pyatigorsk . The great Russian poet ASPushkin wanders the Maashuk Mountains, which inspired his poems and fell in love with M. Yu. Lermontov. He walks in the cities of Azerbaijan, Yerevan and Tiflis and, inspired by the life of the people living there, writes the poems "Sea of Blue", "The dawn has faded", "Yolchi", "One event does not leave my mind" and "Nakhshon". " writes the epic. In 1932, his first collection "Conversation with the Sun" was published.

See, the 20-year-old has achieved creative maturity so quickly that the master of small lyrical poems has enriched Uzbek literature with his large-scale epics in a short period of time . Literary scholar and poet O'tkir Rashid interprets: " *Usman Nasir's second epic "Nakhshan" was written as a result of the poet's travel impressions. The miserable life of an Armenian girl in prison is described. This theme can be said to be the same as the theme of the Norbota saga .*

Here, we have in our hands the collection "Unutmas meny bogim" published forty-four years after the death of our poet, who died early in prisons in a faraway frozen land. The book contains his poems, epics and drama. In the words of Erkin Vahidov, a famous and honored creator of our nation, who is a follower of Usman Nasir: " *Talent is such a gem that it is also a gem in a shell at the bottom of the sea; talent is such a brilliant stream that every drop has the power of rivers and the depth of oceans ; talent is such a flower that in each unopened bud there is freshness the length of a field.*

Usman Nasir's talent was such a gem, such a tributary, such a bud . It's a pity that the unjust society and the authoritarian system have spoiled the rare gem, muddied the beautiful river, cruelly find the most beautiful bud. However, malice did not reach his intention. The garden created by Usman Nasir, the rose leaf that Usman Nasir made bloomed again. Poem masterpieces were transferred from language to language, grafted from heart to heart. He found a unique bright and brighter second life, continued after March 9, 1944, when his life ended tragically...

My poem! you are fine again

If you enter the garden, the flowers are a shame.

It's not me, it's life itself,

You live in me like my soul .

Nationalism is embedded in his blood and soul. In the heart of his burning feelings, his verses are written, and every poem is dressed in a beautiful dress, even if he is wounded by the pain. Sorrow does not like complaints, even sorrow seeks joy in them. And finally, the words of the poet turn into a pattern of the heart . Therefore, his favorite poems become more beautiful in his eyes than the flowers in the garden of elegance. In the sonnet "Yana Sherimga" he expresses his consent to any fate:

My whole life depends on you .

May I spit blood in the morning.

I am crazy, my poem, you are Lyly!

What a sacrifice to bet one's life on poetry. It is lit - the word is lit. Fire is more precious to the heart. After all, he is the singer of the land and the land who turned his heart into music , hidden the moon in his awake eyes - the hunter of the palace of milky rains, the collector of pure feelings:

Heart, you are my voice,

my tongue a flute .

my eyes ,

Heart, you are my lover.

He prays with his faithful friend - the heart. He is ready to describe his feelings until his tongue is tired. It's not a tattoo on the left breast , but every second a word sounds like it shakes the body. Depression is alien to the poet. The spirit has wings. When in the mood . Isn't he thankful that he is alive, that he survived the sufferings of hunger and poverty as a child, looking for music on the streets .

You missed this blue crack,

Your joy overflowed from the shore .

My tongue gets tired, sometimes

You are being translated.

Osman Nasir's imagination is wide. The heart guides the way in an unusual way that illuminates life . Instead of following in his footsteps, he wants to follow his heart. He caressingly says the word with beautiful words . When he was alive, he wanted to pour out his pains and transfer them to his poems, realizing that he was a treasure in a very rich world. He never considers himself a loser, he does not consider himself a winner. Joe shkhin gives the advantage of life to his bosom, to his life partner.

You, oh, you are a playful charmer,

Look for the light in victory.

full , overflow, play,

I'm alive, go sing.

The expression of lyrical emotions is directly related to social activism . Why do you need a heart? We will find the answer to the question in the last paragraph. How impressively the philosophy of living was imprinted on paper in the mind of a twenty-one-year-old student of the Samarkand Pedagogical Academy . If we interpret it from the point of view of the times, Usman Nasir is the leader of his peers, and most importantly, he is a clear goal, a warm hearted beggar.

The sense of ownership of the heart and at the same time the maturity of the heart are in harmony , raising the filial duty to the people and the Motherland to a high status in his poem. A condition imposed sharply in the tone of a command, an invitation, by itself gives up the obstacle to a vital and truthful judgment.

Obey!

If from you

If the country does not agree ,

Yoril, turn into lightning,

Yaril! Okay, I'll just die .

The word "Yoril" that is repeated at the beginning of the line, which increases the effectiveness, sounds first as an emphasis, then as an exhortation. In both cases, the poet is worthy of honor. Being able to do anything with the heart is an absolute truth. If the approval of the Motherland is not achieved, then there is no retreat . One thing. The verdict is final. The poet emphasizes not to be dissatisfied with the fact that the heart shines, disintegrates, cuts the night like lightning for a

moment, makes way for the light, and fades away because it cannot fully justify the trust . He prefers to die for his service than to lose the Fatherland's approval. That's it, hello! Here is the philosophy of self-sacrifice, here is the bravery and decisiveness of the lyrical hero.

of Uzbekistan , clever literary critic Ibrahim Gafurov: " *Looking at such bright lyrical poems, it can be observed that the beginning of the topics that are developing in Uzbek poetry started with Usman Nasir's poems .*" In other words, we would not be wrong to say that Usman Nasir laid the foundation for a unique new school of 20th-century Uzbek lyric poetry of struggle, sentiments related to the interests of the Motherland and the people .

change , renewal, living and flourishing in his inner world made his career as a poet skyrocket. The spring in his mind moved to his work. No one could deny how right he was when he boasted about " my garden ".

Oh, how charming he is!

full of light .

The flowers are almost

I drink them.

Spring is bright in my heart ...

created hurriedly and passionately, as if he was worried that he would leave the flower bed of literature prematurely . In ten years (1927-1937) he created a blessed artistic threshing floor lasting for several decades, attracted the people of the literary world. At the age of twenty-three, as if noticing the ghost of death , he looked at the garden of future creativity behind him and even had time to finish his boast:

If I break off like a leaf,

Don't forget my garden .

respects my work

He builds a statue of flowers,

Even after thousands of years

Don't forget my garden !

Poets know well that the essence of a poem is its meaning, the beauty of a poem is its artistic expression, the impressiveness of a poem is its melodiousness, the contagiousness of a poem is its easy readability and easy readability Usman Nasir's poetry is not alien to any of these. On the contrary, it is still living without losing its modernity and elegance due to its completeness and simplicity . He is educating the young generation. Years are powerless, time is powerless in front of his repeated and emphatic lines. We remember the poet with the pride of patriotism and say: "Don't forget you, your garden! " Spring never leaves your garden , Usman Nasir Baba!" we have every right to say.

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